

Mental health issue during the COVID-19 pandemic

Dwi Jazimah Wijayati, Eko Priyo Purnomo, Aqil Teguh Fathani

Departement of Government Affairs and Administration, Jusuf Kalla School of Government, Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jul 25, 2022

Revised Feb 19, 2023

Accepted Mar 7, 2023

Keywords:

Bibliometric
COVID-19
Mental health

ABSTRACT

One of the sustainable development goals (SDGs) is point 3: good health and well-being. This study aims to determine how people's mental health fared during the COVID-19 pandemic. A library review is the most appropriate method to analyze mental health issues during the COVID-19 pandemic for the past three years. This study is based on articles that met international standards and data collected while searching for a database on Scopus. The results of the study on mental health issues during this pandemic were quite bad because of several government policies that changed people's lifestyles, causing various levels of anxiety in the community so that stress and depression emerged in the community, even though the government decided to break the chain of the spread of COVID-19. Factors that affect mental health during the pandemic, namely significant lifestyle changes that limit the space for people to move, which result in depression, stress, and sleep disturbances that can cause death, become a pressure on the community, which can worsen people's thinking and result in a decrease in community immunity. Ignorance and fear of the COVID-19 pandemic, with lockdowns and the economic crisis, have increased mental illness leading to suicide.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](#) license.

Corresponding Author:

Dwi Jazimah Wijayati
Department of Government Affairs and Administration, Jusuf Kalla School of Government,
Muhammadiyah University Yogyakarta
Yogyakarta, Indonesia
Email: dwijazimah07@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

The 2015–2030 sustainable development goals (SDGs) began in 2016 and officially replaced the millennium development goals (MDGs) 2000–2015 [1]. The SDGs have 17 goals, with 169 targets describing global development goals [2]. One of the sustainable development goals (SDGs) is point 3: good health and well-being related to current health issues. This study aimed to determine how people's mental health fared during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The world is gripped by fear and chaos due to the coronavirus-19; more than 200 countries have been infected with the COVID-19 virus up to this point [3]. The Coronavirus was first discovered in Wuhan, China, on December 31, 2019. It was designated as a human-to-human transmission of the coronavirus infection in 2019 [4]. This virus is known to have first appeared in the seafood and animal market in Wuhan City and was identified as a cause of respiratory disease [5]. The amount of information about COVID-19 during this pandemic is increasing every day, and more data on transmission and its route, reservoir, incubation period, symptoms, and clinical outcomes, including survival rates, are being collected around the world [6]. The global handling of COVID-19 has diverted people's attention away from individually transmitted psychosocial infections. As a result of this pandemic, mental health problems may arise due to the long-lasting COVID-19 pandemic. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on mental health cannot be

fully measured. However, information about the pandemic's impact on mental health can be found in similar cases discovered during the MERS-CoV outbreak in South Korea in 2015 [7]. Public health emergencies, social distancing, self-isolation, quarantine, and restrictions on community activities may affect people's mental health [8]. An important aspect of realizing comprehensive mental health is mental health. In some developing countries, mental health issues are still not prioritized over other infectious diseases.

On World Mental Health Day, commemorated on October 10, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) emphasized the impact of life changes due to the COVID-19 pandemic. It emphasized the need to pay attention to people's mentalities. Currently, almost all people worldwide are affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has hurt people's mental health conditions [9]. Mental health disorders often hide from real, broad-spectrum views [10]. WHO has identified mental health as an integral component of the response to COVID-19 [11]. In light of the mental health problems in the COVID-19 pandemic, this article will discuss the global situation regarding the mental health of people in the world as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. The mentally ill is one of the most vulnerable citizens in society [12].

Studies on severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) survivors showed that in the medium and long term, 41–65% of survivors experienced various psychological disorders, according to Maunder Maunder [13]. A Hong Kong study showed that the psychological problems of SARS survivors did not diminish within a year of the incident. An estimated 64% of survivors could develop a psychiatric disorder. According to Lee's research, the COVID-19 pandemic is a non-natural disaster that can influence everyone's mental health and psychosocial conditions. Significant changes in mental health policies were triggered by the COVID-19 crisis in five key areas: legislation, regulation, financing, accountability, and workforce development. Specific considerations for mental health policy are discussed, including the social determinants of health, innovative technologies, and research and evaluation [14]. The United States imposed stay-at-home orders to reduce the spread of the novel Coronavirus, potentially leading to chronic social isolation and increased loneliness, with 43% of respondents scoring above the published limit and strongly associated with greater depression and suicidal ideation [15]. One month after the December 2019 COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan, China, the affected population had negative changes in cognition or mood and hyperarousal [16].

Making the proper policy choice becomes essential to limiting the effects of a pandemic situation [17]. During the government's policy to self-isolate during the COVID-19 pandemic, most people are experiencing self-reported loneliness. This situation was mostly found in prolonged stay-at-home efforts during the pandemic, likely to increase loneliness and minimize social relationships among many people. Loneliness has been linked to various mental health problems, interpersonal problems, substance use, and physical health conditions, including cognitive decline and increased morbidity and mortality [18]. Individuals who relate to physical, cognitive, and event factors can change their emotions [19]. The term "mental health" comes from the concept of "mental hygiene"; the word "mental" is taken from Greek, which means "soul" in Latin [20].

Mental health has an important role to play. Mental health contributes to the optimal functioning of individuals, families, and communities following developmental tasks during the COVID-19 pandemic [21]. This stress can be caused directly by trauma, such as the death of a family member or co-worker, or a crisis, such as relationship difficulties [22]. There are three main principles in understanding mental health: human nature, man's relationship with the environment, and man's relationship with God [23]. Mental health requires the integration of the physical and the mental by expanding knowledge to shape the self and understanding to adapt to having the capacity to change circumstances and the individual [24]. Mental health and well-being can be influenced by various factors, including genetics, family or friend relationships, physiological functioning, lifestyle, work, social, economic, cultural, political, educational, and other environmental factors [25]. During the COVID-19 pandemic, these factors have been influential in putting pressure on everyone. Everyone needs to take care of mental health to avoid physical complaints because when a person is stressed, the immune system in the body will decrease [26].

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Based on the purpose of the study, which is to analyze mental health problems during the COVID-19 pandemic for the past three years (2020-2022), a literature review is the most appropriate method. The source of this research came from an international standard article with data collection looking for a database from Scopus. Scopus is the widest database with international standards derived from scientific journals, conference proceedings, and books. Some data were analyzed descriptively based on the year of publication, name or journal of publication, research topic, publishing institution, and country of publication. This study employs the literature review method of research. This study was conducted to understand better mental health issues during the COVID-19 pandemic. Process data from Scopus was exported into RIS

export format and then processed with VOSviewer to make a bibliometric map based on the main theme to show the results of this research, which was good health and well-being.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Learn development trends

The trend of research developments on good health and well-being vaccinations during the COVID-19 pandemic began in 2020. In the following year, the graph increased in the last two years, where studies on the COVID-19 vaccine developed according to cases and handling efforts. The COVID-19 pandemic appeared in 2019, but publications on good health and well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic began in 2020; data from 2020 to 2022 had 2,663 documents published. The highest number of documents is in 2021, with 1,532, and the lowest is in 2022, with only 411 documents. Trends in mental health analysis in the last three years, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Publications on mental health in the last three years

The 15 articles contributed the most to the scope database regarding good health and well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic. The second picture shows that most publications are in the United States, with 727 articles, followed by India, 352 articles, and several other countries. Of all the articles, there are eight countries with the highest publication contributions as in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The eight countries with the most publication contributions

3.2. Visualization of mental health research during the COVID-19 pandemic

A network between topics was found based on research on mental health problems during the COVID-19 pandemic. The number of topics found was 2,663 articles from July 2019 to July 2021. Bibliometric analysis was performed with overlay visualization and Vosviewer network details. Network visualization with keywords: The image below depicts the COVID-19 Era mental health issues and the processed data obtained by keywords, which frequently appear with colors indicating groupings. This bibliometric grouping maps images in detail, and clusters provide an overview and general insight. Each circle represents a keyword that appears frequently, and its size depends on the topics related to the relevant article. Five items stand out: SARS-CoV, system, participants, learners, and mental health. The result of this network visualization show that mental health has greatly affected life in the last three year.

With the keywords “good health, “well-being,” “pandemic,” and “COVID-19,” whose data is processed with Vosviewer, the results are grouped, namely four clusters (2 dominant clusters and two minority clusters) with yellow, red, blue, and green colors. VOSviewer groups into four clusters: action, behavioral, case, and actor. The cluster grouping can be seen as follows. Table 1 classifies VOSviewer results based on cluster analysis

Table 1. VOSviewer cluster analysis

Classifies	Cluster analysis
Cluster 1 red (22 items)	Actions, Applications, Best Practices, Challenges, Physicians, Communications, Development, Diagnosis, Efforts, Goals, Guidelines, Healthcare, Management, Nurses, Processes, Public Health, Safety, Services, Society, Systems, Technology, Telemedicine
Cluster 2 green (22 items)	Attitudes, behavior, depression, distress, women, healthcare workers, lockdown, mental health, older adults, online surveys, participants, physical activity, psychological distress, relationships, respondents, self, sleep, social isolation, social support, stress, students, surveys
Cluster 3 blue (14 items)	Cases, China, Coronavirus, Death, Medicines, Global Pandemic, Infection, Death, Region, Sars Cov, Transmission, Vaccination, Vaccines, WHO
Cluster 4 yellow (4 items)	Children, Families, Parents, Schools

Source: Author Analyze

These unfavorable situations resulted in the government making various policies to deal with the COVID-19 problem by issuing a large-scale social restrictions (PSBB) policy [27]. In response to the COVID-19 problem, governments have implemented school closures, travel restrictions, general prohibitions, emergency education funding, alternate means of providing social services, and other varied measures to limit the spread of the virus and adoption rates [28]. The epidemic status of COVID-19 can lead to increased stress, leading to mental health problems such as anxiety and despair [29]. One of the factors affecting mental health is the fear of being infected with the virus of Coronavirus’s emergence, which continues the fear of losing a job during the pandemic because it affects people’s economics [30]. In addition, factors that are quite influential are environmental factors, such as information about the patients and the enactment of various policies during the pandemic [31]. The increase in psychosocial disorders due to mandatory quarantine to combat lockdowns imposed during the national COVID-19 pandemic can lead to severe anxiety, panic attacks, hoarding, paranoia, despair, and long-term post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) [32].

Cluster 4 analysis in yellow also shows that the elderly is more susceptible to COVID-19. The elderly are vulnerable during the COVID-19 pandemic due to decreased immunity and co-morbidities that increase the possibility of death, and the elderly are psychologically influenced by information about COVID-19 [33]. COVID-19 infected 80,565 patients and killed 3,015 people in China until March 5, 2020. Based on Chinese statistics, the case fatality rate (CRF) in patients over 60 is much higher than the overall CRF [34]. Typical deaths over 60 account for 81% of total deaths, which has implications for old age nationally [35]. In other words, older and vulnerable groups must receive psychological support [36]. Other groups are susceptible to exposure to COVID-19, such as people with chronic diseases, smokers and vape smokers, men, and with type A blood [37]. However, apart from those who are vulnerable to exposure to COVID-19, the results of the cluster analysis show that children and families are also affected.

The COVID-19 pandemic may be less common than previously thought, and the impact of pandemic-related symptoms on adolescent well-being and mental health is unknown [38]. Factors that affect adolescent psychosocial development during the COVID-19 pandemic are self, family, and school conflicts [39]. Children who had to learn from home due to social limitations needed assistance from their parents. They also have many obstacles that can be ineffective and inefficient [40]. This condition is new for children at a growing age, so they need to adapt to virtual educational situations. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a

3.2.1. Factors affecting mental health

The global impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on mental health has been tremendous. Treatment is needed, such as psychological assistance and special care for patients and health workers. The number of fatalities is increasing along with the changing situation that impacts the economy. The economy continues to deteriorate as the tourism, aviation, agriculture, and banking industries close due to the COVID-19 pandemic influencing socioeconomic mobility in Indonesia. The link between the COVID-19 pandemic and socioeconomic mobility can be positive or negative [45]. Ignorance and fear of the COVID-19 epidemic, along with lockdowns and economic crises, have resulted in increased suicides and mental illnesses, often followed by suicides. During the COVID-19 pandemic, many papers reported evidence of depression, anxiety, post traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and other psychiatric disorders in the global community. During the COVID-19 outbreak, economic problems increased societal fear and stress [46]. Factors affecting mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic, such as fears of contracting the virus, job loss, concerns about bad news or fake news, economic downturns, and social constraints, commonly known as PSBB, are factors that lead to poor mental health [47].

The mental health of the general public has deteriorated as more people are experiencing anxiety, fear, and irritability when children and adolescents cannot play, learn, or connect with their peers. Depression is increasing among students, especially those who will face university entrance exams [48]. Preparedness for disasters can reduce the psychological impact of disasters [49]. Government and education mitigation strategies regarding COVID-19 have a simple but sustained impact on mood and behavior, especially in students [50]. There is great anxiety when dealing with COVID-19 because of various government policies for handling COVID-19 that change people's lifestyles and cause fatigue, mood disorders, and insomnia. In addition, quarantine can increase stress, anger, and sadness in people who usually do activities involving meeting many people. Lack of communication with family or loved ones during quarantine or hospitalization can lead to psychological instability.

From the results, 648 articles were obtained. After being filtered again, the remaining 19 articles are suitable for this article. There are 12 articles out of 19 that show symptoms of depression. Women are more prone to depression than men, and students show symptoms that can lead to despair [51]. Women and unmarried people experience greater mental health declines than the rest of society [52]. Married individuals cope better with less stress and have high self-esteem [53]. Other factors include the environment you live in, poor health, loneliness, divorce, low money, quarantine, fear of contracting COVID-19, medical history, not being able to find a job, not having children, finding someone close to you who has COVID-19, and others [54]. It is divided into two factors affecting mental health in the COVID-19 era: individual and social factors. Individual factors include personality, physical condition, psychological condition, mindset, and social factors related to social circumstances and environment. Factors affecting mental health include significant lifestyle changes that limit movement, resulting in depression, stress, and sleep disturbances, even death; this community pressure can worsen people's thinking, resulting in a decrease in immune immunity. The community and government should feel concerned and prioritize tackling deviant behavior, as it may lead to unwanted events.

4. CONCLUSION

The mental health system has changed rapidly during the pandemic, and the ongoing response to the challenges posed by COVID-19 is sufficient to raise concerns about people's mental health issues during the COVID-19 pandemic. Mental health problems during this pandemic are bad because of several government policies that change people's lifestyles, causing various anxieties in the community so that stress and depression appear in society. Significant lifestyle changes that limit people's wiggle room and cause despair, stress, and sleep disturbances that lead to death, affecting mental health during COVID-19. These factors put pressure on society, which can intensify people's thinking and reduce their immunity. Along with lockdowns and economic crises, ignorance and fear about the COVID-19 outbreak have contributed to increased suicides and mental disorders.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to all institutions who supported in this research such as Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta, Indonesia, and Khon Kaen University, Thailand. We also thank the four anonymous reviewers and the editors for their insightful comments during the peer-reviewed process. For the funding, authors declare that no funds, grants, or other support were received during the preparation of this manuscript.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Fukuda-Parr, "From the millennium development goals to the sustainable development goals: shifts in purpose, concept, and politics of global goal setting for development," *Gender & Development*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 43–52, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1080/13552074.2016.1145895.
- [2] L. I. Fuldauer, S. Thacker, R. A. Haggis, F. Fuso-Nerini, R. J. Nicholls, and J. W. Hall, "Targeting climate adaptation to safeguard and advance the Sustainable Development Goals," *Nature Communications*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41467-022-31202-w.
- [3] L. Y. Tang and J. Wang, "Anesthesia and COVID-19: What We Should Know and What We Should Do," *Seminars in Cardiothoracic and Vascular Anesthesia*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 127–137, 2020, doi: 10.1177/1089253220921590.
- [4] A. Awadasseid, Y. Wu, Y. Tanaka, and W. Zhang, "Initial success in the identification and management of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) indicates human-to-human transmission in wuhan, china," *International Journal of Biological Sciences*, vol. 16, no. 11, pp. 1846–1860, 2020, doi: 10.7150/ijbs.45018.
- [5] F. Wu *et al.*, "A new coronavirus associated with human respiratory disease in China," *Nature*, vol. 579, no. 7798, pp. 265–269, 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41586-020-2008-3.
- [6] V. M. Corman *et al.*, "Detection of 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) by real-time RT-PCR," *Euro Surveillance*, no. December, pp. 1–8, 2020, doi: 10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2020.25.3.2000045.
- [7] W. Yoo and D. H. Choi, "Predictors of expressing and receiving information on social networking sites during MERS-CoV outbreak in South Korea," *Journal of Risk Research*, vol. 23, no. 7–8, pp. 912–927, 2020, doi: 10.1080/13669877.2019.1569105.
- [8] S. Mukhtar, "Pakistanis' mental health during the COVID-19," *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, vol. 51, no. April, pp. 2018–2019, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102127.
- [9] E. A. Barrett *et al.*, "The COVID-19 pandemic impact on wellbeing and mental health in people with psychotic and bipolar disorders," *Brain and Behavior*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 1–18, 2022, doi: 10.1002/brb3.2559.
- [10] V. Hermann, N. Durbeej, A. Karlsson, and A. Sarkadi, "'Feeling down one evening doesn't count as having mental health problems'—Swedish adolescents' conceptual views of mental health," *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, no. October, pp. 1–14, 2022, doi: 10.1111/jan.15496.
- [11] World Health Organization, *The impact of COVID-19 on mental, neurological and substance use services*, World Health Organization, no. November. 2020.
- [12] S. Adu-Gyamfi, "Mental health service in Ghana: A review of the case," *International Journal of Public Health Science (IJPHS)*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 299–313, 2017, doi: 10.11591/ijphs.v6i4.8474.
- [13] B. Wang, Z. Miao, B. Wan, and X. Xu, "Prevention for post-traumatic stress disorder after the COVID-19 epidemic: Lessons from the SARS epidemic," *Stress and Brain*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2021, doi: 10.26599/sab.2020.9060007.
- [14] M. L. Goldman *et al.*, "Mental health policy in the Era of COVID-19," *Psychiatric Services*, vol. 71, no. 11, pp. 1158–1162, 2020, doi: 10.1176/APPL.PS.202000219.
- [15] W. D. S. Killgore, S. A. Cloonan, E. C. Taylor, and N. S. Dailey, "Loneliness: A signature mental health concern in the era of COVID-19," *Psychiatry Research*, vol. 290, no. May, p. 113117, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113117.
- [16] N. Liu *et al.*, "Prevalence and predictors of PTSS during COVID-19 outbreak in China hardest-hit areas: Gender differences matter," *Psychiatry Research*, vol. 287, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.psychres.2020.112921.
- [17] A. Dewi *et al.*, "Global policy responses to the COVID-19 pandemic: proportionate adaptation and policy experimentation: a study of country policy response variation to the COVID-19 pandemic," *Health Promotion Perspectives*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 359–365, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.34172/hpp.2020.54.
- [18] I. Ingram *et al.*, "Loneliness among people with substance use problems: A narrative systematic review," *Drug and Alcohol Review*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 447–483, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1111/dar.13064.
- [19] M. Fernández Cruz *et al.*, "Evaluation of the emotional and cognitive regulation of young people in a lockdown situation due to the COVID-19 pandemic," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 11, no. October, 2020, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.565503.
- [20] M. D. A. Malek, "Mental health and social work: The islamic perspectives," *Mental Health and Social Work*, pp. 395–413, 2020, doi: 10.1007/978-981-13-6975-9.
- [21] M. M. Barry, A. M. Clarke, I. Petersen, and R. Jenkins, *Implementing mental health promotion*. Springer, 2019.
- [22] E. L. Tempest, B. Carter, C. R. Beck, and G. J. Rubin, "Secondary stressors are associated with probable psychological morbidity after flooding: A cross-sectional analysis," *European Journal of Public Health*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 1042–1047, 2017, doi: 10.1093/eurpub/ckx182.
- [23] M. Bisri, P. A. A. I. Karsiyanto, A. C. Az Zahra, and T. Chusniyah, "Emotion-focused coping strategies as predictors of new inmates' adjustment in the pandemic era," *KnE Social Sciences*, vol. 2020, pp. 21–31, 2021, doi: 10.18502/kss.v4i15.8186.
- [24] L. Liebenberg, "Reconsidering interactive resilience processes in mental health: Implications for child and youth services," *Journal of Community Psychology*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 1365–1380, 2020, doi: 10.1002/jcop.22331.
- [25] F. Martela and K. M. Sheldon, "Clarifying the concept of well-being: psychological need satisfaction as the common core connecting eudaimonic and subjective well-being," *Review of General Psychology*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 458–474, 2019, doi: 10.1177/1089268019880886.
- [26] H. Samji *et al.*, "Review: Mental health impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on children and youth – a systematic review," *Child and Adolescent Mental Health*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 173–189, 2022, doi: 10.1111/camh.12501.
- [27] R. D. M. Kumala, "Legal analysis of government policy on large scale social restrictions in handling COVID-19," *The Indonesian Journal of International Clinical Legal Education*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 181–200, 2020, doi: 10.15294/ijicle.v2i2.38326.
- [28] E. P. Purnomo *et al.*, "ASEAN policy responses to COVID-19 pandemic: Adaptation and experimentation policy: A study of ASEAN countries policy volatility for COVID-19 pandemic," *SAGE Open*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 215824402210821, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1177/21582440221082145.
- [29] D. Pettinicchio, M. Maroto, L. Chai, and M. Lukk, "Findings from an online survey on the mental health effects of COVID-19 on Canadians with disabilities and chronic health conditions," *Disability and Health Journal*, vol. 14, no. 3, p. 101085, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.dhjo.2021.101085.
- [30] Bilal Ahmad Bhat *et al.*, "A study on impact of COVID-19 lockdown on psychological health, economy and social life with special reference to karur district of Tamilnadu, India," *Gedrag & Organisatie Review*, vol. 33, no. 03, pp. 36–46, 2020, doi: 10.37896/gor33.03/443.
- [31] Z. Asif *et al.*, "Dynamics of SARS-CoV-2 spreading under the influence of environmental factors and strategies to tackle the pandemic: A systematic review," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 81, no. March 2022, p. 103840, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.scs.2022.103840.
- [32] M. J. Dubey, R. Ghosh, S. Chatterjee, P. Biswas, S. Chatterjee, and S. Dubey, "COVID-19 and addiction," *Diabetes & Metabolic*

- Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 817–823, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.dsx.2020.06.008.
- [33] S. Pant, S. Bajracharya, M. Subedi, and P. Chair, “Smriti Pant: Impact of COVID-19 on the elderly,” *Journal of Patan Academy of Health Sciences*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 32–38, 2020.
- [34] C. Huang *et al.*, “Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China,” *The Lancet*, vol. 395, no. 10223, pp. 497–506, 2020, doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30183-5.
- [35] L. Fu *et al.*, “Clinical characteristics of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) in China: A systematic review and meta-analysis,” *Journal of Infection*, vol. 80, no. 6, pp. 656–665, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jinf.2020.03.041.
- [36] K. Lee, G. C. Jeong, and J. Yim, “Consideration of the psychological and mental health of the elderly during COVID-19: A theoretical review,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 21, pp. 1–11, 2020, doi: 10.3390/ijerph17218098.
- [37] K. Blalock, F. Breve, G. Varrassi, P. Magnusson, and J. Pergolizzi, “Vaping and subsequent comorbidities potentially associated with increased mortality and more severe illness in covid-19: A narrative review,” *Signa Vitae*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 25–36, 2021, doi: 10.22514/sv.2021.113.
- [38] J. Blankenburg *et al.*, “Comparison of mental health outcomes in seropositive and seronegative adolescents during the COVID19 pandemic,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-06166-y.
- [39] M. S. Amran, “Psychosocial risk factors associated with mental health of adolescents amidst the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak,” *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 6–8, 2022, doi: 10.1177/0020764020971008.
- [40] E. Munastiwi and S. Puryono, “Unprepared management decreases education performance in kindergartens during Covid-19 pandemic,” *Heliyon*, vol. 7, no. 5, p. e07138, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07138.
- [41] M. Shevlin *et al.*, “Anxiety, depression, traumatic stress and COVID-19-related anxiety in the UK general population during the COVID-19 pandemic,” *BJPsych Open*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 1–9, 2020, doi: 10.1192/bjo.2020.109.
- [42] D. Rahmadani, I. Chastanti, and D. A. Harahap, “Parents’ role in biology learning during the COVID-19 pandemic,” *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*, vol. 7, no. 2, p. 137, 2021, doi: 10.29303/jppipa.v7i2.583.
- [43] M. M. Prinzing, J. Zhou, T. N. West, K. D. Le Nguyen, J. L. Wells, and B. L. Fredrickson, “Staying ‘in sync’ with others during COVID-19: Perceived positivity resonance mediates cross-sectional and longitudinal links between trait resilience and mental health,” *Journal of Positive Psychology*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 440–455, 2022, doi: 10.1080/17439760.2020.1858336.
- [44] S. Widati and A. Siddiq Amer Nordin, “Mental health during COVID-19: An overview in online mass media Indonesia,” *Asia Pacific Journal of Public Health*, vol. 34, no. 2–3, pp. 300–301, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1177/10105395211063169.
- [45] N. Prawoto, E. P. Purnomo, and A. A. Zahra, “The impacts of COVID-19 pandemic on socio-economic mobility in Indonesia,” *International Journal of Economics and Business Administration*, vol. VIII, no. Issue 3, pp. 57–71, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.35808/ijeba/486.
- [46] M. Shammii, M. Bodrud-Doza, A. R. M. Towfiqul Islam, and M. M. Rahman, “COVID-19 pandemic, socioeconomic crisis and human stress in resource-limited settings: A case from Bangladesh,” *Heliyon*, vol. 6, no. 5, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04063.
- [47] N. K. Fauk, Ernawati, E. Dent, G. A. Asa, and P. R. Ward, “Impact of COVID-19 lockdowns on the activity and mental health of older people in Indonesia: a qualitative study,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 20, 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijerph192013115.
- [48] I. Giannopoulou, V. Efstathiou, G. Triantafyllou, P. Korkoliakou, and A. Douzenis, “Adding stress to the stressed: Senior high school students’ mental health amidst the COVID-19 nationwide lockdown in Greece,” *Psychiatry Research*, vol. 295, no. August 2020, p. 113560, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113560.
- [49] L. S. Palupi, “Is psychological preparedness for potential disaster difference between gender among university students,” *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 698, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/698/1/012011.
- [50] W. E. Copeland *et al.*, “Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on college student mental health and wellness,” *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, vol. 60, no. 1, pp. 134–141, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jaac.2020.08.466.
- [51] J. Pope, E. K. Olander, S. Leitao, S. Meaney, and K. Matvienko-Sikar, “Prenatal stress, health, and health behaviours during the COVID-19 pandemic: An international survey,” *Women and Birth*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 272–279, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.wombi.2021.03.007.
- [52] M. Almeida, A. D. Shrestha, D. Stojanac, and L. J. Miller, “The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on women’s mental health,” *Archives of Women’s Mental Health*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 741–748, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s00737-020-01092-2.
- [53] A. M. Lawal, E. O. Alhassan, H. O. Mogaji, I. M. Odoh, and E. A. Essien, “Differential effect of gender, marital status, religion, ethnicity, education and employment status on mental health during COVID-19 lockdown in Nigeria,” *Psychology, Health and Medicine*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 1–12, 2022, doi: 10.1080/13548506.2020.1865548.
- [54] J. J. V. Bavel *et al.*, “Using social and behavioural science to support COVID-19 pandemic response,” *Nature Human Behaviour*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 460–471, 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41562-020-0884-z.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Dwi Jazimah Wijayati is a Master Student at Departement of Government Affairs and Administration, Jusuf Kalla School of Government, Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta. She interested in public services and Government. She can be contacted by email: dwijazimah07@gmail.com.

Eko Priyo Purnomo is a full professor at the Department of Government Affairs and Administration, Jusuf Kalla School of Government, Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta. Currently, He is also the Director of E-Governance and Sustainability Institute (ESI). He is interested in how to create and implement alternative policies that allow for natural resource extraction while sustaining the community's growth and livelihood. He believes that one of Indonesia's fundamental problems is the uneven distribution of resources (money, authority, nature, and knowledge). Eko has previously collaborated on research and served as a Visiting Professor at Korea University, Korea; the University of Maryland College Park, the US; Khon Kaen University, Thailand; University Utara Malaysia, Malaysia; and the University of Cambridge, the UK. He can be contacted by email: eko@umy.ac.id.

Aqil Teguh Fathani is a Doctoral Student at Policy Studies, Andalas University. His research focuses on Sustainable Policy, Government, and Governance. He is also the public administration of Batam Putera University Batam. He can be contacted by email: aqil.teguh.psc19@mail.umy.ac.id.